

Effect of Insecticide Carbofuran & Fungicide Bavistin on Certain Rice-field Nitrogen-fixing Blue-green Algae

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Abstract

During the past few decades, pesticides have been used frenziedly though, it is not a good measure of sustainable practice. The non-target effects of pesticides in soil posed a major problem in recent years and micro-algae becomes the first in the list of non-target organisms that are affected by pesticides (Mahapatra *et al.*, 2003). The present investigation was designed to study the tolerance level of certain nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae to pesticides. Here, commercial preparations of insecticide Carbofuran & fungicide Bavistin were used at concentrations varying from 50 ppm to 400 ppm and the tested blue-green algal species were *Anabaena variabilis*, *Aulosira fertilissima*, *Calothrix marchica*, *Cylindrospermum* sp., *Microcystis aeruginosa*, *Nostoc muscorum*, *Scytonema* sp., *Tolypothrix tenuis* and *Wesolopsis prolifica* isolated from Rice-fields of Majkuchi area of Kamrup district Assam. All these tested algal species were found to be more or less sensitive to Carbofuran except *Anabaena variabilis* and *Wesolopsis prolifica* which were found to be tolerant to 200 ppm concentration of Carbofuran. In case of Bavistin all the algal species were found to be more or less tolerant except *Calothrix marchica* which was found to be very sensitive.

Keywords

Carbofuran and Bavistin, Blue-Green Algae, Tolerant, Sensitive.

Introduction

The blue-green algae are the group of micro-organisms that are mostly connected to the rice cultivation. In rice-field many blue-green algae contribute greatly to the nitrogen economy and add availability of crop nutrients and increases crop yield. The ability of rice to grow year after year in the absence of manure is due to the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen by BGA (Singh, 1961, Sweta, 2016).

Since the start of global 'green revolution' in 1960s, commercial agriculture pursues the use of high-yielding varieties of crops, which need constant input of agrochemicals such as chemical fertilizers and pesticides. However, the addition of agrochemicals to any agro-ecosystems, affects the dynamic equilibrium of soils (Padhy and Rath, 2015), by eliminating a part of non-target useful soil flora and fauna (Galhano *et al.*, 2011, Kumar *et al.*, 2016).

In rice-fields the large-scale use of pesticide chemicals causes contamination of soil and water and cause effect on non-target microorganisms (Bhuyan and Sarma, 2004). Studies on the interaction of algal flora with agrochemicals have been widely conducted, but there has been an increased attention paid to pesticides.

In agricultural fields nitrogen-fixing Cyanobacteria shows high variation in their tolerance limits to the effects of different pesticides (Dixit and Tewari, 1992). Venkataraman and Rajyalakshmi (1972) reported that ceresin, cotoran, delapon, dithane, diuron etc. inhibit the growth of certain species of *Anabaena*, *Nostoc*, *Aulosira* and *Tolypothrix*. At lower concentrations stimulatory effects was observed on *Tolypothrix tenuis* and *Calothrix brevissima* (Ibrahim, 1972).

Objective of study

The present study was designed to test the tolerance level of nine species of nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae (isolated from rice-fields) to different concentration of insecticide Carbofuran and Fungicide Bavistin.

Review of Literature

The pesticides used in modern agriculture, beside their effects on target organisms, have a wide range of effects on non-target organisms. The effects of various pesticides on beneficial microalgae have been studied under defined conditions.

Venkataraman and Rajalakshmi, 1972 studied relative tolerance of nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae to pesticides.

Ahmed and Venkataramn (1973) studied on tolerance of *Aulosira fertilissima* pesticides.

Dixit and Tewari (1992) studied on effect of pesticides on certain nitrogen fixing blue-green algae and found different tolerance level to the tested pesticides.

Choudhury and Sarma (2001) studies on effects of pesticides on certain algae from Tea-garden soil.

Singh (2019) studies on tolerance level of blue-green algae to different pesticides (Dimecron, Malathion and Butachlor).

Few other notable works done in this field were – Tarar and Shewale, 1984; Pandey and Kashyap, 1986; Megharaj *et al.*, 1990; Dikshit *et al.*, 1992; Dikshit and Tiwari, 1992; Islam, 2007; Ghadai *et al.*, 2010; Kumar *et al.*, 2012; Manikar *et al.*, 2013; Padhy *et al.*, 2014; Padhi and Rath, 2015; Chaurasia 2014; Shinde 2018, 2021; Choudhury and Kalita 2020, Nayak and Panigrahi 2023 etc.

Methodology

Pure culture of nine species of blue green algae *Anabaena variabilis*, *Aulosira fertilisima*, *Calothrix marchica*, *Cylindrospermum* sp., *Microcystis aeruginosa*, *Nostoc muscorum*, *Tolypothrix tenuis*, *Scytonema* sp. and *Westiellopsis prolifica* were prepared from the samples collected from rice-fields of Majkuchi village of South Kamrup district of Assam during the year 2023 following the method adopted by Ferris and Hirsch (1991). The algal species were identified following standard literature (Desikachary, 1959, Prescott, 1961, Bellinger and Sigee, 2010), cultured on Hughe's medium (Allen 1968) and the P^H of the medium was adjusted at level 8.

To observe the pesticidal effect, different concentration of pesticides were mixed in ppm level (50 – 400 ppm) with the cultures in an experimental series and culture without pesticide was served as control. The cultures were maintained following standard procedures (Allen and Stanier, 1968; Andersen, 2005). The appearances of algal species were observed under microscope after 21 days of incubation period.

Result and Discussion

Pesticide Carbofuran was tolerated by *Annabaena variabilis* and *Westolopsis prolifica* up to 200 ppm concentration while it was found toxic to *Aulosira fertilisima*, *Calothrix marchica* and *Scytonema* sp. were not able to grow in the tested concentration of Carbofuran. Rest of the species showed moderate tolerant to this pesticide. The species *Nostoc muscorum* was able to survive up to 100 ppm and *Microcystis aeruginosa*, *Cylindrospermum* sp. and *Tolypothrix tenuis* were not able to grow at the concentration higher than 50 ppm (Table 1 & Fig, 1).

In case of Bavistin *Anabaena variabilis*, *Westolopsis prolifica* were found to be tolerant which up to 300 ppm concentration while *Calothrix marchica* was found highly sensitive to this pesticide and not able to grow in even at lower concentration of Bavistin. The species *Nostoc muscorum* and *Cylindrospermum* sp. were also tolerant to this pesticide which were also able to survive up to 200 ppm concentration. On the other hand, *Mycrocystis aeruginosa* was able to survive up to 100 ppm and *Aulosira fertilisima*, *Scytonema* sp. and *Tolypothrix tenuis* were not able to survive after 50 ppm concentration of Bavistin (Table 2 & Fig, 1).

Table - 1: - Appearance of algal species in various concentration of Carbofuran at 21 days of incubation period.

Name of algal species	Concentration of Carbofuran treatment				
	50	100	200	300	400
<i>Anabaena variabilis</i> Kutz	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Aulosira fertilisima</i> Ghose	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Calothrix marchica</i> Lemmerm	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Cylindrospermum</i> sp.	+	-	-	-	-
<i>Mycrocystis aeruginosa</i> Kutz	+	-	-	-	-
<i>Nostoc muscorum</i> Agardh.	+	+	-	-	-
<i>Scytonemas</i> sp.	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Tolypothrix tenuis</i> Kutz	+	-	-	-	-
<i>Westolopsis prolifica</i> Jnet	+	+	+	-	-

+ = appeared; - = not appeared

Table 2: - Appearance of algal species in various concentration of Bavistin at 21 days of incubation

Algal species	Concentration of Bavistin treatment				
	50	100	200	300	400
<i>Anabaena variabilis</i> Kutz	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Aulosira fertilisima</i> Ghose	+	-	-	-	-
<i>Calothrix marchica</i> Lemmerm	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Cylindrospermum</i> sp.	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Mycrocystis aeruginosa</i> Kutz	+	+	-	-	-
<i>Nostoc muscorum</i> Agardh.	+	+	+	-	-

<i>Scytonemas</i> sp.	+	-	-	-	-
<i>Tolypothrix tenuis</i> Kutz	+	-	-	-	-
<i>Westolopsis prolifica</i> Jnet	+	+	+	+	-

+ = appeared; - = not appeared

In the observations of Gangawane (1980), *Calothrix* sp. was observed as sensitive to Bavistin even at a very lower concentration, that finding was in conformity with the present observation where species *Calothrix marchica* was found toxic to both the pesticides.

In this study *Aulosira fertilissima* was appeared as sensitive form which is supported by the findings of Tandon *et al* (1988), Ahmed and Venkataraman (1973), Gangawawane (1990), Choudhury & Sarma (2001).

The present experiment shows that in case of these tested algae Carbofuran is more toxic than Bavistin. *Anabaena variabilis* and *Westolopsis prolifica* were the most tolerant species which can tolerate up to 300 ppm concentration in fungicide Bavistin and up to 200 ppm in insecticide Carbofuran. The overall results of this investigation indicate that fungicide Bavistin is less harmful to nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae than Carbofuran insecticide. The present observations also supported by the findings of Torres and Lawrance (1976), Choudhury and Kalita (2013).

Conclusion

In the present investigation it was found that the insecticide Carbofuran is more toxic to non-target micro-algae than fungicide Bavistin. These observations indicate that the pesticidal effect on algae is species specific and high doses of pesticides may cause adverse effects on survival of the beneficial non targeted nitrogen-fixing algal forms. So, it is necessary to screen efficient nitrogen-fixing blue-green algal species those are capable of growing and fixing nitrogen at higher rate even in presence of recommended doses of the pesticides, before their inoculation into the agricultural field.

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